

**ESTABLISHMENT OF PRIVATIZATION OF LAND PLOTS
PRIVATIZATION OF CIVIL-LEGAL REGULATION BASIS.**

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Abstract: In this thesis, the formation of the foundations of civil-legal regulation of the privatization of land plots, the de-monopoly of land ownership, the environment of civil-legal nihilism, the Prince of Torrenc for honest owners, innovative electronic government technologies, the separation of special privatization legislation from civil legislation are revealed.

Key words: monopoly, state property, civil-legal nihilism, Torrenc principle, land plot, privatization.

After gaining independence, Uzbekistan inherited the territory from the former Soviet state, where all land belonged to the state, the monopoly owner. Undoubtedly, this structure of land ownership did not contribute to the economic changes that began in the first half of the 90s of the 20th century. As noted by V.V. Kostetsky, the transition to a market economy is predetermined by factors such as private property and appropriate forms of management. Privatization was an integral part of this process. It is for this reason that land reform began in New Uzbekistan, one of its main tasks was to introduce the institution of private land ownership as an important regulator of land relations in the market economy.

Land privatization, as one of the leading directions of land reform, is aimed at providing the monopoly of land ownership by replacing the principle of exclusive state ownership of land with the principle of pluralism of forms of land ownership in the mechanism of legal regulation of land relations. The first principle is characterized by the single subject composition of the institution of land ownership, which makes it possible to designate land only in state (people) ownership. The principle of pluralism of forms of land ownership implies the possibility of obtaining plots of land in the ownership of different subjects, among which the state is only one of them.

¹Macmillan D.C. (2000). An economic case for land reform. *Land Use Policy*, 17, 49-57.

At the current stage of state formation, privatization in Uzbekistan is carried out in the context of economic reforms and the search for ways to provide all sectors of the economy with investment resources. At the same time, this field is accompanied by significant insecurity of the property rights of subjects participating in the process of privatization, which in turn leads to the violation of civil and economic legislation, creates an environment of civil-legal nihilism, and creates a particularly negative reality in the conditions of the imperative features of civil legislation.

In this regard, according to V.Shcherbina's opinion, the legislation on privatization consists not only of laws in terms of the form of normative documents, but also a set of other normative legal documents that regulate property-legal and organizational relations regarding the privatization of state property¹.

There are reasonable opinions of researchers about dividing the complex of regulatory and legal regulation of these social relations into a separate sub-branch of civil law. The problem of legal regulation of privatization relations from the point of view of separation of special privatization legislation from civil legislation has been researched several times and different points of view have been expressed in this regard, of course. For example, A.Kh.Trofimov comes to the following conclusions: despite the complex nature of privatization legislation, which represents civil-legal and administrative-legal norms, privatization legislation is regulated by a single civil-legal method due to the classification of methods of influence, and in this regard, the legislation on privatization is civil it is appropriate to interpret it as a sub-field of law. According to this scientist, such an approach allows paying attention to the specific features of privatization legislation while maintaining the unity of the civil-legal regulation method. Yu.V. Aldanov rightly defines the legal nature of the legislation on privatization, and at the stage of modern development, as a special complex institution, the legal norms of privatization take priority in comparison with the general norms of civil legislation under the conditions of a certain place and time, in particular, the rules for the implementation and execution of privatization transactions, as well as the legal relations in the field of privatization such priority is evident in the issues related to the legal status of individuals and legal entities as a relevant subject.

Shcherbina V.S. *Gospodarske right: a clerk. 5th view., Rev. and additional* - Kiev: Yurinkom inter, 2008. - 720 p.

² Trofimova A.Kh. *The relevance of legal regulation of civil and privatization legislation. Lawyer. 2012. - No. 1. - C. 25-26..*

In our opinion, in accordance with the appropriate description given above by Yu.V.Aldanov, the privatization legislation, by its nature, acquires a special complex tone and at the same time creates a mixture of norms of civil, administrative, financial and other spheres of law. However, in terms of content, priority should be given to norms of civil law. Because in the future, taking into account the development of social relations in the field of ownership, the legislation of privatization should fully guarantee the rights of persons who have acquired property rights on a special basis in the future.

A sign of the creativity of the norm of the privatization contract is its orientation (goal) regarding the transfer of property to private ownership. This criterion is a unifying sign that belongs to the group of obligations regarding the transfer of property to the privatization contract. However, N.V. Gorina rightly points out that the privatization contract has its own content (like any civil law contract), taking into account that each contractual relationship is characterized not only by certain unifying features, but also by specific features. According to this researcher, this is caused not only by the factual actions of the privatization participants, but also by actions that have a full economic and legal description and are therefore legally important. In the privatization contract, the fact of transferring the rights of ownership, use and disposal of the property to another person is also important.

In 7 of the 25 countries of the Eastern European Partnership (for example, Armenia, Georgia, Azerbaijan, Moldova, Ukraine), agricultural land was privatized in the late 1990s and early 2000s through the distribution of physical plots. Plots are distributed among the villagers. In the countries outside the former SSR, the reform was carried out in this way only in Albania, Hungary and partly in Romania.

Distribution of real estate rights in Belarus According to the data of the state land cadastre, as of January 1, 2016, 79 percent of the registered land plots were in state ownership. If we calculate by area, the share is even bigger, 98% of land plots belong to the state. Such a distribution in 90% of the territory of Belarus is occupied by immovable properties according to their natural origin: forests, agricultural land, water bodies. For such lands, the laws of the country envisage the sole owner - the state. Thus, the distribution of private property rights is possible in less than 10% of the country's territory. These are lands intended for housing construction and maintenance, homesteading, horticulture and agriculture. At the beginning of 2016, the area of land plots registered for

residential construction and service was less than 3% of all registered land plots.

It should be noted that different countries had different starting points for starting land distribution. In some countries (Albania, USSR) all agricultural land belonged to the state. In other countries (Yugoslavia, Poland) part of the land was already converted into private property with the beginning of the land reform. What conclusions can be drawn from the results of the first stage of land reform? First, it is recognized that the first phase of land reform in Eastern European partner countries had negative consequences, especially for agricultural land. In many countries, the newly established structures of land users proved to be unfit to compete with the global and Western European economies. The phenomenon of the reform was the fragmentation of land due to small and medium farms. Land reform has led to a gap between the efficiency of small farms and large farms. Many new farmers had access to the necessary machinery. Fragmentation means that land is divided among many owners of small and often poorly formed plots.

Secondly, is it appropriate to talk about the lack of land reform when, as in Uzbekistan, land ownership still belongs mainly to one owner - the state? One of the main goals of land reform is to create a real estate market, i.e. land plots together with the buildings, structures, and surrounding buildings located on them. A properly organized market should ensure a natural redistribution of rights to real estate, where ownership is transferred to a more efficient user. The peculiarity of Uzbekistan is that the land reform started not with the land, but with the buildings located on it. In fact, more than 80% of residential properties in Uzbekistan are privatized, which exceeds the number of such privatizations in Germany (46%). There is a rule here that in some cases the rights to the plots of land are subordinate to the property rights in relation to the building. An alternative market of rental rights has been formed in Uzbekistan. The transfer of rental rights can serve as the subject of a pledge. Land reform used different methods from other countries. Along with privatization, alternative methods such as public-private partnerships, especially in infrastructure creation, are steadily developing. Ownership of capital equipment (buildings, structures) is allowed to all subjects of civil law, including foreigners.

The results of land administration reform in all countries of the Eastern European Partnership can be considered successful without exception. This is evidenced by the high ranking of DoingBusiness-2016 in the "Property Registration" section of the World Bank. Eastern European cooperation

countries are in the highest rating groups: Lithuania - 2, Georgia - 3, Belarus - 5, Estonia - 6, Slovakia - 7, Kyrgyzstan - 8, Russia - 9.

The question arises why the land administration reform, which is very expensive, is included in the most important part of the land reform? In this place, it is necessary to remember its founder, Sir Robert Torrens, who proposed the land registration system in 1858. The introduction of the new Torrens system aims to guarantee title to property. The Torrens system is a non-conflict registration of rights and charges; is based on the principles of non-conflict of rights of purchasers who acquire property in good faith and for a fee. The concept of "honest owner of real estate" is the basis for the full civil handling of real estate, protection of investors and creation of a good investment environment.

In Estonia, the principles of the Torrens system are defined by the Laws "On Social Rights" and "On the Serf Book", which were adopted as part of the reforms of 1992-1994. Estonian State Real Estate Cadastre is one of the most perfect in Europe in terms of accounting and regulation of real estate turnover. Torrent principles for honest owners are not always observed in Uzbekistan. In this sense, there are prospects for improving the land management system. Recently, there is more and more talk about another task of land administration - to ensure all potential possibilities of rational land management. The drivers of this approach are new technologies, public-private partnerships and open data.

Traditionally, land management functions are one of the main directions of management activities in the field of land fund protection and use. Functions of land resources management are defined and defined by the state in relevant legal norms. Generally, the general and most important functions of management are distinguished: provision of land to individuals and legal entities for economic activity and other purposes; planning for rational use and protection of land resources; organization and conduct of land management, land monitoring; state control over land use and protection; fiscal activity; participation in the settlement of land disputes; protection of property rights and land use rights in relation to land; legal provision of rational land use and land protection².

In Uzbekistan, hundreds of regulatory legal documents are related to the regulation of land relations and the real estate market. It is appropriate to pay attention to only four cases related to them. First, this stage of land reform is considered incomplete in all countries of the European partnership. Second,

² Hartvigsen M. Land Reform and Land Fragmentation in Central and Eastern Europe // Land Use Policy. 2014. Vol. 35. P. 77-81.

there is a digital transformation of society in the world. This means that traditional management processes, not land resources, are becoming obsolete before our eyes.

Traditional technologies are innovative e-government technologies: multi-level ultra-high-precision remote sensing of the earth in combination with artificial intelligence technologies; ERP and CRM systems to support real estate asset management; modeling of BIM and other "digital construction" technologies; spatial data infrastructure and unified geographical area management platform; cloud SaaS, PaaS technologies; big data; 3D rights, 3D regional planning, 3D cadastre; E-participation, electronic information, electronic consulting; Being replaced by GNSS/GPS etc.

Thirdly, any management system must have its own quality indicators, a mechanism for continuous control of this quality, and be established for continuous quality improvement. Many countries of the Eastern European Partnership (Georgia, Moldova, Ukraine, Serbia, Croatia, etc.) have created such a system based on the LGAF (Land Governance Assessment Framework) methodology of the World Bank. The development of a continuous monitoring system on a real-time scale continues. In contrast, the quality of management in Uzbekistan is not evaluated in any way.

Fourth, it should be noted that land redistribution methods have recently emerged that minimize the use of expropriation. Such methods include, in particular, the Pilar methodology developed by the UN structure GLTN-UN Habitat.

1. Creation of national spatial data infrastructure. It is recommended to adopt the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the National Spatial Information Infrastructure" in order to ensure the land formation processes of the country. It is recommended that the draft law be based on the INSPIRE directive of the European Union.

2. Implementation of PILaR land management methodology. Such a measure, if not excluded, minimizes the processes of expropriation of property in land development.

3. Introduction of systematic formation of real estate. It is clear that such formation should be carried out in a certain area by conducting complex cadastral work at the expense of local budgets and correcting all errors in previously registered land plots. In cases where small changes have occurred in the area of land plots, it is advisable to introduce a rule that state registration of changes in real estate objects is carried out by the state registrar without the

participation of the right holder. It seems appropriate to introduce the concept of "fuzzy boundaries" into legislation for objects of natural origin, their legal status and simplified methods of mass formation of such objects based on remote sensing data. It is recommended to carry out individual identification of a part of real estate objects based on the declarations of their right holders. The proposed measure ensures completeness of the cadastre and simplifies property tax management.

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